

POLITICAL SCIENCES

THE ARCHITECTURE OF NATO'S RESPONSE TO CRISES: ESSENTIAL PREREQUISITE FOR SUCCESS

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Abstract

NATO's Crisis Response System (NCRS) is a complex instrument through which the Alliance addresses political-military crises, consisting of a wide range of mechanisms (organizational, operational, planning) that ensure a coordinated and prompt response to the cause or threat of a crisis through the use of appropriate means. The analytical exploration, in a critical manner, of doctrinal elements through the algorithmization of the decision-making process, the procedural development of NATO decisions in crisis/crises, and the evaluation of the lesson-learning process constitute robust arguments for validating how the organization sizes its crisis response.

Keywords: crises, strategic concept, confrontation, transformation, projection, adaptation

Preamble

North Atlantic Treaty Organization was primarily conceived as a defensive military alliance, aimed at uniting individual forces and doctrines into a synergistic system capable of addressing extreme situations and, of utmost significance, proactively countering emerging threats. During the organization's early days in April 1949, Western Europe's primary objective was to restore the strategic balance against the expansionism of the USSR. (Fix and Keil, 2022)

As the era of *cold bipolarism* waned, NATO underwent a transformation from a defense-focused organization to a security-oriented one. It commenced providing its members and partners a spectrum of security services, ranging from immediate protection to long-term collaboration. A pivotal moment in this evolution was marked by Poland's alignment with the West, leading to shifts in power dynamics in Central Europe and NATO's integration into an area that had been dominated by the Soviet Union for nearly half a century. Over time, the Alliance expanded progressively, establishing a global network of 31 member states and forming partnerships with over 40 countries and organizations spanning five continents. The organization is dedicated to acting resolutely, with flexibility, pragmatism, and innovation, all in the pursuit of building and fortifying global security. Subsequently, after the end of the Cold War, the United States enjoyed a unipolar moment (Krauthammer, 1990). Corollary, the Russian Federation primarily focuses its attention on states within its sphere of influence, with the exception of the Baltic region, which predates the dissolution of the Soviet Union.¹ On a different perspective, Russian Federation considers the Baltic states to be the most vulnerable part of NATO... (Miklaucic, 2023).

Recent history exposed an unprepared world, unable to effectively mitigate past crises or quell emerging ones. As an illustrative and transformative crisis,

the COVID-19 pandemic has emerged, evolved, and receded. The pandemic emerged as an unprecedented challenge for contemporary generations due to the unique nature of its spread. Beyond its medical impact and the constraints it imposes on freedom of movement, the crisis, known generically as COVID-19, has hastened the resurgence of past crises, with profound implications for global boundaries.

A thorough and fair analysis of the effects and consequences following the end of a crisis represents an initial step towards anticipating future disruptions and systemic preparedness for amplified impact. During a crisis, beyond the efforts of management and resolution, there is the probability that the very physical existence of an entity (institutional, state, transnational) may be reconsidered towards contrasting, defending, and securitizing its foundational purpose.

Summarized, but by no means superficial, the analysis of the war at the eastern extremity of NATO's borders reveals a set of lessons learned and, at the same time, rules to follow for the future of the European and global security landscape. (Cordesman, 2022)

The most pressing lesson from the Ukrainian war may be the delineation and the transition into the realm of plausibility of a direct military confrontation between NATO and the Russian Federation (RAND Corporation, 2023). The incursion (repeated but total and somewhat state-sanctioned) of the Russian Federation beyond the territories of the separatist pseudo-state entities into the heart of Ukraine represents a new black milestone in continental history by reintroducing armed conflict into the realm of state politics. For more than two decades, starting after the relaxation of tensions in the Balkan region, Europe has not witnessed conventional military confrontations. The sole prevailing threat was isolated terrorism. In other words, continental-scale warfare has once again become plausible with Russia's westward offensive (Levy, 2023). When making an argument, it's important to note that the security

¹ The shaded area includes Belarus, Ukraine, Moldova, Armenia, Azerbaijan, Georgia, Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Tajikistan, Turkmenistan and Uzbekistan. At the same time, we emphasize the fact that near abroad does not have an undisputed geographical area. See Radin A., Reach C.

(2017), 'Russian views of the international order', RAND Corporation. Available online at: https://www.rand.org/pubs/research_reports/RR1826.html (Accessed: 12 October 2023)

environment among major actors often reaches a critical boiling point in cyclical terms. In this context, we emphasize the contemporary relevance of the Herzian concept of the security dilemma.²

Nevertheless, of incredible importance for the years ahead, the Russian Federation's intervention in Ukraine has tested the already eroded allied cohesion. The organizational response has been timely and coordinated up to the present. In any scenario, the erosion caused by an external crisis on an entity, in this case, NATO, represents, beyond the systemic shock, an opportunity for adjustment, adaptation, and/or regeneration (LSE IDEAS, 2023).

The Alliance stands out due to its uniqueness, singularity, and atypical ethos. On one hand, it is an inter-governmental structure that doesn't rely on the principle of national sovereignty and the veto rights of each member state. On the other hand, from a systemic perspective, NATO's defining elements are shaped beyond the individual/private interests of the states.

An accurate analysis of NATO's systemic transformations must encompass the repetitive, constant features of current political-military crises. However, much more constructively, it should also uncover their particularities in relation to doctrinal adjustments and changes within operational aspects.

Contemporaneity naturally derives from the lessons of the past; however, a misinterpreted, incomplete, or erroneous interpretation of these lessons recurrently brings humanity, through the decisions or inactions of major actors, to the brink of a global conflict. In the light of the present and the backdrop of wide-scale challenges for the repositioning of the Alliance's eastern neighborhood in a discretionary and violent manner, organic transformations of NATO are unfolding.

We return to the rhetoric regarding the opportunity offered by a crisis, emphasizing the duality of the aforementioned one. Beyond the negative aspect of individual, state, and/or global threats, a path emerges for individual reset and systemic reconfiguration under the auspices of the current crossroads. Today, amidst security volatility, territorial uncertainty, the complexity of subsequent crises, and the ambiguity inherent in NATO's solutions, the results of the expeditionary war against terrorism, primarily conducted on the frontlines in Afghanistan, are not well defined. Nevertheless, NATO finds itself once again in the position of a security outpost for the entire European continent against the violent expansion of the Russian Federation (Aronsson and Deni, 2023).

NATO versus crises - past, present and future

By reducing reality to its founding principles, NATO is poised between adaptation and/or revolution. The crossroads overlaps the major turbulences of the security environment, viewed from the perspective of

any of the members: in the logical sequence national-European-trans-Atlantic-planetary. Adaptation develops in paradigmatic change, processual transformation and institutional reformation. In contrast, organizational revolution would entail re-founding, deep review, institutional rebuilding and major restructuring.

The North Atlantic Treaty, under the auspices of its form and substance, was comprehensive and justifiable for all the historical balances traversed by the organization. We recall, in chronological logic, the Cold War, the expansion of the Alliance after the fall of the Berlin Wall, the operations outside the fined territory (Kosovo and Afghanistan) and the cohesion of the members against the scourge called terrorism. The trend denotes a global approach to political-military crises, whilst the process of developing the new strategic concept came to an end. The argument for taking a new strategic approach is represented by the volatility, uncertainty, complexity and, above all, the ambiguity of the global security environment.

The Strategic Concept adopted at the NATO Summit in Madrid, Spain resulted from the need to adapt the command structures, resources, capabilities structures and agencies to the current security environment. The updated concept bolstered the fundamental foundations of the organization (core tasks), incorporating the operational capacities necessary to thrive in the age of crises. generic goal of global peace to which NATO aims is transposed into the 3 essential organizational tasks (Strategic Concept, 2023):

- *deterrence and defense* (previously mentioned as *collective defense*) - by which NATO members reaffirm their obligation to provide mutual assistance both in case of external aggression on any member and in the event of an emerging threat to the security of any member. Also, NATO will significantly strengthen the posture to deny any potential adversary and possible opportunities for aggression.

- *crisis prevention and management* (augmented from *crisis management*)- through which the Alliance is committed to getting involved, using a variety of political-military methods and means, in preventing potential crises that can affect the security of the organization, in managing those already triggered and in strengthening the post-conflict stability, if it ensures value of Alliance security; this issue continues the holistic approach, which means that all Member States, as well as partner states, must adapt their policies and actions in a coherent manner in order to prevent and manage crises.

- *cooperative security* (derived from *security through cooperation*)- through which NATO will be involved in international security issues, acting both in the direction of establishing partnerships with countries or international organizations relevant for maintaining

² According to Herz J.H., the security dilemma arises from the individual's awareness that others seek to destroy him, therefore there is always a need for self-defense, which in turn can make others feel insecure. What is true for individuals is equally relevant to understanding group behavior. In fact, Herz argues that the security dilemma is more acute in groups for the simple reason that they can develop means of self-defense that are far more destructive than those of individuals.

Moreover, as they come to equate their identity and value with that of the group to which they belong, individuals may be prepared to sacrifice their lives in the name of group survival. Thus, even if the most optimistic hypothesis is made about the nature and motives of individuals and groups, the security dilemma will persist as long as there are groups that do not submit to a higher authority. In the modern world, these are sovereign states.

a stable security environment, and in the direction of arms control, for their non-proliferation. Corollarily, the organization is open for European democracies who want to join it.

In total congruence with the core tasks, regarding the institutional response facing potential crises, the Alliance developed a Crisis Response System (NCRS). The system is connected with the NATO Intelligence and Warning System (NIWS), ensuring the functional support of the three related processes: The NATO Crisis Management Process (NATO Crisis Management Process/NCMP), NATO's Operational Planning Process/NOPP and, respectively, the NATO Civil Emergency Planning Crisis Management Arrangements. The complementarity and synergy of the mentioned elements ensure the success of the efforts undertaken by the Alliance in crisis management.

The integration of constituent elements and the optimal functionality of disparate parts within the whole is a procedural process that follows six stages - NATO Crisis Management Process.

Phase 1: Indicators received through the NATO Warning and Information System provide the North Atlantic Council (CAN/NAC) with four options: (a) decide that no further consideration is required (inaction); (b) direct NATO vigilance in order to provide more information for the Council (channelling the effort); (c) consider preventive diplomatic and political responses, including civil emergency interventions, taking into account military implications, as appropriate; or (d) decides to initiate a full assessment of the crisis situation in order to proceed to the next phases.

Phases 2 and 3: NAC tasks (NAC Initiating Directive/NID) the relevant political and military committees to assess the crisis and advise on the developing crisis situation and its implications for Alliance security (evaluative political- military). At the moment, SACEUR is tasked by the Council to develop a response strategy.

As a result, the Council may select one of the response options by providing formal political direction to NATO military authorities regarding operational planning for the chosen option.

Phase 4 (Planning): The SACEUR must develop the concept of operation (CONOPS) and subsequently a plan of operation (OPLAN) and submit them to the Military Committee for approval and the North Atlantic Council for review and approval. The action stage starts simultaneously with the decision of the Council for formal authorization (NAC Execution Directive/NED).

Phase 5 (Execution): NATO conducts and executes the mission (in the light of political decisions and directives), conducting periodic reviews of the operation (Periodic Mission Review/PMR) in order to quantify the progress made towards the final objective and correlate/adjust the military response provided, its capabilities and force structure.

Phase 6 (Transition): In this phase, NATO consid-

ers and implements a handover to the competent authorities, completes the military mission and progressively withdraws its forces; the success of the operation would translate into a return to stability.

The primacy of NATO cohesion and unity is imposed to limit self-triggered/self-determined vulnerabilities. Prominent leaders of the member states competed in luring statements, later proven excessive, affecting, however, the protection capacity of the ensemble.

It is no less true that all history reveals the balances that NATO not only survived, but used them in favor of multiplying and increasing organizational strength: we recall here the Turkey-Greece rivalry, the attempt to overthrow the regime in Cyprus, the withdrawal of France from the military structures and the relocation of headquarters from Paris to Brussels, Ronald Reagan's Star Wars Program³, George W. Bush's war on terror and terrorism and the perspective split from the time of Iraq 2003. Beyond these operational and/or decisional touchstones and tests, NATO has built a consensual dialogue among allies and survived by preserving the fundamentals of collective defense. In essence, the Alliance sought an agreement in all these disagreements (*we agree to disagree*).

Further, in the historical downstream of facts, the Russian Federation keeps NATO alive, but alert, Moscow's behavior being obviously offensive, an aspect proven by the annexation of Crimea, the aggression in Eastern Ukraine, the call for military combat substances as chemical weapons, the interference in the electoral process, the solid nuclear threat and the conventional and hybrid danger on the Eastern flank and, once again, the aggression in Ukraine. The Alliance's reactive approach to Russian threats must be systemically dimensioned, but also channeled in relation to the level of formulated, perceived and/or real risks, and, most importantly, in conjunction with the European effort (Cancian and Monaghan, 2023).

European cohesion

Both NATO and the European Union are engaged in a cycle of continuous adaptation, generating, as a corollary, a process of reflection meant to rebuild (at this epochal moment, with applicability foreseen for a decade, at least) the pillars of strategic security thinking.

We consider that NATO, in a contrasting allegory to the European Union, which needed to adopt generative modifications and successive treaties for empowerment and survival, is the result and beneficiary of a visionary and comprehensive foundational document (even in these tumultuous times). This institutional advantage provides the path and response for adaptation.

The stake of the guiding products of the two organizations - NATO's new *Strategic Concept* and the EU's new *Strategic Compass* - should be represented by the congruence of common goals, potentials and design of tasks. In addition, synergistically, those two aforementioned deal with security competences, as follows:

³ The Strategic Defense Initiative (SDI), derisively nicknamed the Star Wars program, was a proposed missile defense system intended to protect the United States from attack by ballistic strategic nuclear weapons (intercontinental

ballistic missiles and submarine-launched ballistic missiles). The concept was announced on March 23, 1983, by President of the United States (POTUS) Ronald Reagan.

the primacy of territorial defense and the prevalence of resilience, the identification of the way to design the operational effort, in the twilight of expeditionary operations and defense planning, simultaneously with the development of capabilities (Biscop, 2021).

The matter of NATO-EU cooperation is recurrent and imperative (Tardy and Lindstrom, 2019), being at the center of the development of the EU's Common Security and Defense Policy (CSDP) since the end of the 1990s. The discussion is divided into three levels of debate: the relationship and complementarity between the two entities; the effort of the European states within NATO and the augmentation of the transatlantic link. The need to synergize the security effort of the two defense institutions finds its argument in more than twenty years of inter-institutional debates and cooperation interspersed with a series of unfulfilled objectives and commitments, as well as frictions over duplication, overlap, European strategic autonomy and division tasks (Tardy, 2021).

In the upcoming decade, NATO faces the crystallization of three strategic approaches, each incorporating a range of predominantly controllable political and military actions. However, only one of these approaches truly embodies a balanced strategy for **ensuring strategic stability**. The Alliance could choose a path oriented towards bolstering military capabilities and enhancing postural stability, effectively crafting a force scenario to address potential adversarial dynamics, especially concerning a nuclear adversary operationally positioned on NATO's periphery (Hooft, Ellison and Sweijs, 2023). Nonetheless, it's important to consider that such a partially aggressive stance might introduce unforeseen political and economic disruptions. Alternatively, NATO could revisit a historical lesson by reinforcing its defense posture while simultaneously emphasizing dialogue with the Russian Federation, much like the approach seen in 1967 with the Harmel Report or during the Intermediate-Range Nuclear Forces Treaty (INF) discussions when NATO pursued a **dual strategy** based on robust defense and diplomatic engagement. The boldest among these approaches would involve directly confronting Europe's most significant strategic instability and facilitating the creation of a **new European security architecture**. (Andersson and Cramer, 2023)

Placing NATO permanently (apparently) on the edge of the existential chasm is problematic for at least three reasons. The first argument - the narrative about the crisis is imprecise; the terminal critical point and the dissolution of NATO are equally vague. Secondly, NATO has often exceeded moments of imminent collapse, making the disappearance (dismantling) thesis unlikely and unrealistic. Finally, we can say that the Alliance has an inexhaustible capacity for recovery or regeneration. Of course, mere survival is not enough, it matters how far the being is reflected in the adaptation

to the new realities. Certainty best describes the fact that NATO is a living, transformational and inspirational organization.

Epilogue

Over its 74 years of existence, NATO has experienced both highs and lows, eliciting both tranquility and controversy in the realm of security⁴. Regardless, yet not independently of the status of the political-military ensemble projected externally (recently, within the organization itself), with the two extremes - novelty (robust) and obsolescence (outdated), NATO has found the internal strength to (re)dimension and (re)invent itself. Indeed, recent times have served as a litmus test for NATO's credibility and power. The latter has been making efforts to contain, halt, and prevent the transformation of the pandemic crisis into a security crisis. Today, a real/(in)credible threat is identified in the political and security realm through the violent escalation of the Alliance's eastern flank.

"NATO was created to deal with crisis"⁵ and historical anamnesis provides sufficient reference points for Allied positivity. After the end of the Cold War, the Alliance was deemed structurally redundant. Despite speculations, NATO has survived and is (once again) a bulwark against the Russian Federation.

The North Atlantic Treaty, both in form and substance, has been comprehensive and justifying for all the historical challenges faced by the organization. We recall, in chronological order, the Cold War, the expansion of the Alliance after the fall of the Berlin Wall, operations beyond the amended territory (Kosovo and Afghanistan), and member cohesion against the scourge called terrorism. The trend signifies a global approach to political-military crises on the fringes of the process of implementing the new Strategic Concept. The argument for adopting a new strategic approach is driven by the volatility, uncertainty, complexity, and, above all, ambiguity of the global security environment.

It is no less true that throughout its history, NATO not only survived but used the challenges it faced to its advantage, leading to the multiplication and augmentation of its organizational strength. Here, we recall the rivalry between Turkey and Greece, the attempt to overthrow the regime in Cyprus, France's withdrawal under de Gaulle from military structures and the relocation of the headquarters from Paris to Brussels, the Star Wars initiative and Ronald Reagan's New Missile Defense, George W. Bush's war on terror and terrorism, and the perspective rift from the time of the 2003 Iraq War. Beyond these stones of trial and operational and/or decision-making tests, NATO has built a consensus dialogue among allies and survived by preserving the foundations of collective defense. In essence, the Alliance sought agreement within all these disagreements (*we agree to disagree*).

⁴ NATO intervened, using airstrikes, in Kosovo (March 24 - June 11, 1999) without the approval of the UN Security Council, which set a precedent...

⁵ "NATO was created to deal with crisis. So we can help. And our Alliance is playing its part.", the statement of NATO Secretary-General - Jens Stoltenberg on April 2, 2020, after the

first-ever videoconference meeting of foreign ministers to decide the measures NATO takes in the context of combating the global health crisis caused by the COVID-19 pandemic. Available at: https://www.nato.int/cps/en/natohq/opinions_174772.htm

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